

Let's talk FAIR

creating, finding and (re)using vocabularies in
the Humanities and Social Sciences research

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(3) Vrije Universiteit (VU)

DH Benelux workshop
Amsterdam, June 3, 2025

Introduction

Why this workshop?

- Vocabularies are an essential part of research, data curation, and interoperability, but there is no common understanding of concepts and best practices
 - We will discuss some concepts
 - We have some hands-on activities and discussions on how to create and share vocabularies
- The SSH FAIR Vocabulary Registry has been developed in the past three years, we are launching the production version today!
 - We will introduce it and do a small evaluation

Today's agenda

14:00-14:15 Introductions

14:15-15:15 Main Concepts + hands-on: Create + publish

- Motivation: why do we need vocabularies in SSH (*Angelica*)
- Main concepts & hands-on: create + convert (*Liliana*)
- Publish vocabularies: hands-on & brief discussion (*Menzo*)

15:15-15:30 Coffee/tea break

15.30-16:30 FAIR & the SSH FAIR vocabulary registry (with hands-on)

- FAIR concepts & assessments (*Menzo*)
- Vocabulary reuse: basic concepts (*Liliana*)
- Finding vocabularies in the SSH Vocabulary Registry (intro & hands-on) (*Liliana*)

16:40-17:00 Plenary discussion & conclusion (*Moderated by Angelica*)

Workshop materials
<https://edu.nl/bvxhn>

Introducing each other

- Your name and institution
- Name one vocabulary that you know, have used, or are curious about

Workshop facilitators

Liliana Melgar

- Data specialist at the Digital Infrastructure department of the KNAW Humanities Cluster (HuC)
- Initially trained as librarian. Focus on metadata standards, data modelling, data formats, data interoperability, controlled vocabularies
- Curator of the SSH FAIR vocabulary registry

Workshop facilitators

Menzo Windhouwer

- Lead Engineer Team Structured Data at the Digital Infrastructure department of the KNAW Humanities Cluster (HuC)
 - anything around databases
 - including linked data
- semantic operability has been an ongoing topic for the last 20 years
- as is research infrastructures
 - CLARIN since its start
 - nowadays CLARIAH which combines CLARIN with NDE

Infrastructures

CLARIAH develops, facilitates and stimulates the use of Digital Humanities resources and infrastructures. We offer these resources to researchers and other professionals in an insightful and user-friendly way. (clariah.nl)

CLARIN is a digital infrastructure offering data, tools and services to support research based on language resources. (clarin.eu)

Het Netwerk Digitaal Erfgoed (NDE) stimuleert en faciliteert kennisdeling en samenwerking in de cultuursector. (netwerkdigitaalerfgoed.nl)

Workshop facilitators

Angelica Maineri

- Data manager at the Open Data Infrastructure for Social Science and Economic Innovations (ODISSEI)
- Sociologist and survey methodologist by training, RDM expert by experience
- Bridging between technical and substantive

ODISSEI: A national infrastructure for Social Science

ODISSEI creates a federated data infrastructure for the social and economic sciences in the Netherlands, on behalf of more than 45 member organisations.

SSHOC-NL

A collaboration between
ODISSEI and CLARIAH

The project aims to enable
ground-breaking
interdisciplinary research on
pressing societal question

SSHOC-NL is financed by the
Dutch Research Council
(NWO) Large-scale Research
Infrastructure Grant.

Motivation: why do we need vocabularies in SSH

My dataset is about the state of banks in the
Zuid-Holland region

My dataset is about the state of banks in the Zuid-Holland region

Why vocabularies?

Shared understanding of the world,
disambiguation

→ machine-actionability (FAIR)

Example 1: European Language Social Science Thesaurus (ELSST) by CESSDA

3,400 concepts covering the core social science disciplines

Translated into EU languages

The screenshot displays the ELSST Thesaurus interface for the concept 'EMPLOYMENT'. The top navigation bar includes the title 'ELSST Thesaurus (Version 5 - 2024)', a language dropdown set to 'English', and a search box. The left sidebar shows a hierarchical tree of concepts, with 'EMPLOYMENT' selected. The main content area is titled 'LABOUR AND EMPLOYMENT > EMPLOYMENT' and displays the following information:

PREFERRED TERM	EMPLOYMENT
BROADER CONCEPT	LABOUR AND EMPLOYMENT
NARROWER CONCEPTS	CLANDESTINE EMPLOYMENT EMPLOYMENT ABROAD EMPLOYMENT HISTORY EMPLOYMENT OPPORTUNITIES EMPLOYMENT PROGRAMMES EMPLOYMENT SERVICES HYBRID WORK JOB CHANGING JOB CREATION JOB SHARING JOB VACANCIES MILITARY SERVICE OFFSHORE EMPLOYMENT ON-SITE WORK RESEARCH WORK [show all 22 values]
RELATED CONCEPTS	EMPLOYMENT POLICY RIGHT TO WORK
ENTRY TERMS	JOBS

Banen en lonen op basis van de Polisadministratie

Version 1.0

Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek, 2024, "Banen en lonen op basis van de Polisadministratie", <https://doi.org/10.5793/4/0b01e410807c72a7>, ODISE Portal, V1

Cite Dataset ▾

Learn about [Data Citation Standards](#).

Contact Owner

Share

Dataset Metrics ⓘ

0 Downloads ⓘ

Description ⓘ

In dit databestand zijn kwantitatieve en kwalitatieve gegevens opgenomen over banen en lonen van werknemers bij Nederlandse bedrijven over een bepaald verslagjaar of deel van een verslagjaar. De definitie van "baan" die ten grondslag ligt aan dit bestand is een inkomstenverhouding (IKVID) in verband met arbeid van een werkgever met een persoon. Een persoon kan per werkgever meerdere inkomstenverhoudingen tegelijkertijd hebben. Deze component, waarbij de sleutel voor een baan de inkomstenverhouding (IKVID) is, is beschikbaar vanaf verslagjaar 2010. De poliscomponent is ook beschikbaar voor de verslagjaren 2006 tot en met 2009; hierbij is de baansteutel BAANRUGID en is de naam van de component POLISJJJJBUSVV. Vanaf 2015 verschijnen er van deze component naast de versie met definitieve jaargegevens ook versies van cumulatieve voorlopige maandgegevens. In september 2024 zijn alle versies van 2011 tot en met 2023 beschikbaar.

[Read full Description \[+\]](#)

Subject ⓘ

Social Sciences

Keyword ⓘ

Werkgelegenheid, Loon, Banen, Sociaaleconomische en ruimtelijke statistieken, Arbeid en lonen, Werkgelegenheid en lonen, Banen en loonsommen

License/Data Use Agreement

[Custom Dataset Terms](#)

Enriched Metadata ^

Term ⓘ

ELSSST:

Werkgelegenheid WERKGELEGENHEID <https://elsst.cessda.eu/id/3/aa0ddef6-51fa-4eee-bcb5-2b64c41a4818>

CBS taxonomie:

Arbeid en sociale zekerheid ARBEID EN SOCIALE ZEKERHEID <https://taxonomie.cbs.nl/vocab/id/3840>

CBS begrippen:

Werkgelegenheid WERKGELEGENHEID <https://taxonomie.cbs.nl/vocab/id/20>

CBS begrippen:

Banen BANEN <https://taxonomie.cbs.nl/vocab/id/22>

Frequency of Use ⓘ

high

Example 2: Gender, Sex, and Sexual Orientation (GSSO)

Q woman

Advanced Search Random Entry

81 results found for "woman".

Items Per Page: 10

woman

A person whose identity is female, based on societal and cultural conceptualizations of being female, usually (but not always) reflected by specific anatomical variations, chromosome combinations, and/or sex hormones.

YOUR Gender, Se.

Q assigned female at birth

Advanced Search Random Entry

1 results found for "assigned female at birth".

Items Per Page: 10

assigned female at birth

An assignment of a female gender shortly after birth.

Examples 3: PersonLink

A Multilingual and Multicultural Ontology Representing Family Relationships

BrotherOf^{OP}

[back to ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://cedric.cnam.fr/isisd/ontologies/PersonLink.owl#5.2>

has super-properties

[SiblingOf^{OP}](#)

has domain

[Male^C](#)

has range

[Person^C](#)

ChildOf^{OP}

[back to ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://cedric.cnam.fr/isisd/ontologies/PersonLink.owl#3.1>

has equivalent properties

[child of^{OP}](#)

has super-properties

[DescendantOf^{OP}](#)

has sub-properties

[DaughterOf^{OP}](#), [SonOf^{OP}](#)

Understanding vocabularies... and finding?

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Awesome Ontologies for Digital Humanities

A curated list of ontologies for Digital Humanities

What is an [awesome list](#)?

This list collects useful ontologies, vocabularies, terminologies, and taxonomies for modelling and publishing datasets from Humanities domains as [Linked Data](#). If you wish to contribute, [send a PR](#) or get in touch with [IISG Data & Augmentation](#) or [Albert Meroño](#) or [Melodee Beals](#).

Contents

- [General](#)
- [Computational / Digital Literary Studies](#)
- [Cultural Heritage](#)
- [Fiction Studies](#)
- [Language](#)
- [Musicology](#)
- [Periodicals](#)

<https://github.com/CLARIAH/awesome-humanities-ontologies>

README Code of conduct CC0-1.0 license

Awesome Ontologies for the Social Sciences

What: A curated list of ontologies, controlled vocabularies and semantic artefacts for the social sciences

What is an [awesome list](#)?

This list collects useful ontologies, vocabularies, terminologies, and taxonomies for modelling, publishing and enriching (meta)datasets from the social sciences. If you wish to contribute, please check the [contribution guidelines](#) or get in touch with [Angelica Maineri](#). You can read more about the initiative on the [ODISSEI website](#)
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7852158](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7852158)

Please note that, unless otherwise stated, the resources are in English. When available, the Digital Object Identifier (DOI) assigned by [FAIRsharing](#) is added.

If you want to learn more about semantic artefacts (in general and for the social sciences) we recommend the following resources:

- Controlled vocabularies for the social sciences: what they are, and why we need them [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7157800](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7157800)
- Ontologies vs Taxonomies vs Thesauri, and its place on the Semantic Web [link](#)

Acknowledgments This work is inspired by CLARIAH's [Awesome Ontologies for Digital Humanities](#).

Contents

- [Ontologies look up services](#)
- [General](#)
- [Concepts, Terms, and Variables](#)
- [FAIR data stewardship and RDM](#)
- [International standards](#)
- [Methods and analyses](#)
- [Topics and Subjects](#)

<https://github.com/FAIR-Expertise-Hub/awesome-ontologies-social-sciences>

Vocabulary-related concepts & hands-on: create + convert

Main concepts

A word cloud of related concepts. The words are arranged in a roughly circular pattern. The largest word is 'vocabularies' in dark blue. Other prominent words include 'ontology' in teal, 'controlled vocabularies' in green, 'schema' in purple, 'knowledge graph' in yellow, 'taxonomy' in grey, 'terms' in light green, and 'SKOS' in green. The words are of varying sizes and orientations, creating a dynamic visual effect.

controlled vocabularies
schema ontology
knowledge graph taxonomy
terms
vocabularies
SKOS

In most cases, there are no single agreed-upon definitions

Knowledge Organization Systems (KOS)

Lists

Uncontrolled vs controlled

Property name

Foodstuff	chosen label
courgette	zucchini
zucchini	zucchini
jam	jam
jelly	jam
pie	pie
apple pie	pie
legumes	
fruits and vegetables	
cereals	

Normalization

URIs

- Uniform Resource Identifiers
 - For shared understanding on the Web
- Instead of names or string use URIs both for the values and the properties

Thus, instead of...

Foodstuff	chosen label
courgette	zucchini
zucchini	zucchini

The SKOS namespace URI:

<http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#>

Use SKOS

skos:Concept	skos:prefLabel	skos:altLabel	skos:definition	skos:exactMatch	skos:exactMatch
https://myvocab#zucchini	zucchini	courgette	Edible summer squash, typically green in colour, vegetable	https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q7533	https://lod.nal.usda.gov/nalt/29712

SKOS as RDF

- SKOS is a W3C recommendation that provides a standardized way to represent and share KOS on the web using the Resource Description Framework (RDF).
- This facilitates exchange between computer applications in an interoperable way.

```
skos:prefLabel "zucchini"@en ;  
skos:altLabel "courgette"@en ;  
skos:definition "Edible summer squash, typically green in colour, vegetable"@en ;  
skos:exactMatch <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q7533> ;  
skos:inScheme <https://lod.nal.usda.gov/nalt> .
```

Vocabulary reuse

Turtle -> one of the RDF serialization formats

Taxonomies (for hierarchical relationships)

[NAL Agricultural Thesaurus \(NALT\)](#)

Three kinds of hierarchical relationships

(Hedden, 2022):

1. Generic or generic-specific: "a kind of", e.g., *zucchini is a kind of squash*.
2. Instance: named individuals, e.g., *New Year's Day is a specific instance of holidays*.
3. Whole-part: "is within" or "is a constituent part of", e.g., *Marine biology is a part of biology*.

"Some/all" test

Taxonomies can also be used as "classification" or "categorization" schemes

Contents [hide]	
1	Vegan diets
1.1	Raw Vegan
1.2	High Carb Low Fat Vegan
1.3	Whole Food Plant Based
1.4	Mock-Meat Focused
2	Vegetarian
2.1	Beegan
2.2	Flexi-Vegan
2.3	Ovo-Vegetarian
2.4	Lacto-Vegetarian
3	Non-vegetarian
3.1	OstroVegan
3.2	Flexitarian
3.3	Localvore
3.4	Freegan
3.5	Pescatarian
3.6	Reducitarian
3.7	Parasitivore
3.8	Killing odd order predators

Thesauri (for associative relationships)

Diet

Alternative terms

UF < Diet and nutrition
UF < Eating habits

Broader Terms

BT ↑ Dietetics

More specific terms

NT3 ↓ Diet fads
NT3 ↓ Dietary cholesterol
NT3 ↓ Dietary fats
NT3 ↓ Dietary fibre
NT3 ↓ Dietary proteins
NT3 ↓ Dietary sodium
NT3 ↓ Food preferences
NT3 ↓ Healthy eating
NT3 ↓ Vegetarian diets
NT3 ↓ Weight reduction diet

Related terms

RT ⇌ Dietary surveys

Some types of associative relationships

– An action and an agent or instrument:

Gardening
NT Gardeners

– An action and the production of that action:

Publishing
NT Books

– An action and the location of that action:

Primary Education
NT Primary schools

– An object or action and its role or purpose:

Tanks
NT Water storage

– A profession and the person who practices that profession:

Masonry
NT Masons

– Cause and effect:

Infections
NT Infectious diseases

...

- SKOS only offers the option to say:
`skos:related`
- If you need to specify the type of relation, you need define custom subproperties of `skos:related` for richer semantics:

```
<cause> rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;  
rdfs:subPropertyOf skos:related .
```

Schemas

Food is your “class” or entity type
you will have another class for “dishes”
(it’s recommended to have one “table” per entity type)

Column names = “schema” properties

skos:Concept	skos:prefLabel	skos:altLabel	ex:isIngredientOf
https://lod.nal.usda.gov/nalt/29712	zucchini	courgette	ratatouille

Rows =
instances =
named
individuals

`ex:isIngredientOf rdfs:subPropertyOf skos:related .`

Individual
cells =
“values”

Or, better, you
could reuse an
existing ontology

Ontologies

- Warning! Different definitions... One definition:
 - "An ontology is a 'formal, explicit specification of a shared conceptualization' (Guarino et al. 2009) of a domain of the world. It describes what type of entities can exist in this domain and what relationships they may have. (On the distinction between ontologies and thesauri, cf. Kless et al. 2015.)" (Romein et al., 2023)"

Ingredient	
URI	https://purl.org/ontology/fo/Ingredient
Description	An Ingredient is the combination of a quantity and a food, giving the amount of something that should be used in the recipe.
Properties	food , imperial_quantity , metric_quantity , quantity

Ontology documentation (<https://www.bbc.co.uk/ontologies/food-ontology/#ontologyterms>)

A human-readable version of an ontology (<https://foodon.org/>)

Ontologies

- A basic example ontology in machine-readable format (owl)

```
@prefix rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> .
@prefix owl: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#> .
@prefix ex: <http://example.org/food#> .
@prefix xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> .

### Ontology declaration
<http://example.org/food> a owl:Ontology .

### Classes
ex:FoodItem a owl:Class ;
  rdfs:label "Food Item"@en .

ex:Recipe a owl:Class ;
  rdfs:label "Recipe"@en .

### Object Property
ex:hasIngredient a owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:domain ex:Recipe ;
  rdfs:range ex:FoodItem ;
  rdfs:label "has ingredient"@en .

### Individuals (instances)
ex:Zucchini a ex:FoodItem ;
  rdfs:label "Zucchini"@en .

ex:Ratatouille a ex:Recipe ;
  rdfs:label "Ratatouille"@en ;
  ex:hasIngredient ex:Zucchini .
```

Hands-on

In this practice we will create a taxonomy in SKOS and convert it to turtle

1. Open the folder →
2. Each participant chooses one file: open the file with your position number on the table (left to right)
3. Try to reproduce the taxonomy structure for this term using skos properties, as given in the template (only use altLabel and skos:broader):

<https://lod.nal.usda.gov/nalt/en/page/29712>

Workshop materials

<https://edu.nl/bvxhn>

List of concepts to place in the taxonomy:

<https://lod.nal.usda.gov/nalt/en/page/29712>

squashes

vegetables

zucchini

winter squashes

summer squash

courgette

The screenshot shows the 'NALT Full' taxonomy interface. On the left is a 'Hierarchy' tree with 'zucchini' selected. The main content area displays the following information:

- Plant Production, Gardening / plant products / vegetable products / vegetables / squashes / zucchini [show all 7 paths]
- Fields of Study / plant products / vegetable products / vegetables / squashes / zucchini
- Animals, Livestock, One Health / plant products / vegetable products / vegetables / squashes / zucchini
- Fields of Study / plant products / vegetable products / vegetables / squashes / zucchini

PREFERRED TERM	zucchini
TYPE	Product
BROADER CONCEPT	squashes
SYNONYMS	courgettes summer squash
IS PRODUCT OF	Cucurbita pepo
IN OTHER LANGUAGES	calabacitas Spanish calabacin
URI	https://lod.nal.usda.gov/nalt/29712
DOWNLOAD THIS CONCEPT:	RDF/XML TURTLE JSON-LD Created 1/19/06, last modified 9/5/17
EXACTLY MATCHING CONCEPTS	http://id.agrisemantics.org/gacs/C12554 id.agrisemantics.org http://id.cabi.org/cabt/70502 id.cabi.org marrows aims.fao.org

Alternative tools

- [protege](#)
- [PoolParty](#) (available via [RCE](#))
- [VocBench](#)
- [ontome](#)
- ...

see also <https://registry.vocabs.clariah.nl/guidelines/software/> for a more complete list

and <https://openjournals.ugent.be/dlh/article/id/85751/> for a step by step guide

Publish vocabularies: hands-on & brief discussion

Publish vocabularies: where? who?

- where is closely related to governance
 - who determines where the vocab goes: you as the benevolent dictator or ...
- your institute/university (https://huygens.knaw.nl/vegetables)
 - make it something that you will continue to work on together with your department/team/..
- at your community (https://vegetables.vocab)
 - examples [PiCo](#), [RDA SKG IF](#)
 - core + extensions (concentric modelling)
- at your project (https://globalise.nl/vegetables)
 - but what will happen after the project phase?
- at your infrastructure (https://vocabularies.clarin.eu/clavas/vegetables)
 - [CLARIN](#), [DARIAH](#), CLARIAH, [ODISSEI](#)
- fallback to yourself (https://menzowindhouwer.github.io/vegetables)
 - e.g. git([hub](#)|[lab](#)) pages
 - your own domain, e.g. [PNV](#), [ROAR](#)
- at an archive? (discussion)
 - DANS
- at w3c?
 - community

Publish vocabularies: resolvable URIs

- Persistent Identifier
 - add a level of indirection (PID -> current location -> resource)
 - scheme supported by your institute or university
 - [handle](#)
 - [ARK](#)
 - ...
 - [cool URI](#)
 - see where, with long term support
 - [PURL](#)
 - [w3id](#)
- Semantics or not
 - semantic shift/rot
 - individuals vs properties or classes
 - do you really need new ones? see reuse (later)
 - are there authorities for your instances?

Publish vocabularies: versioning

- keep the semantics stable!
- mergers/splits: keep [provenance](#), mark [deprecated](#) don't delete!
- SSH vocab commons [whitepaper](#) "wholesale versioning"

Publish vocabularies: handson

- [github_pages](#)
- [skosplay](#)
- [skosmos](#)

Coffee/tea break

FAIR principles and FAIR assessments

FAIR principles

In 2016, the '[FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship](#)' were published in *Scientific Data*. The authors intended to provide guidelines to improve the **F**indability, **A**ccessibility, **I**nteroperability, and **R**euse of digital assets. The principles emphasise *machine-actionability* (i.e., the capacity of computational systems to find, access, interoperate, and reuse data with none or minimal human intervention) because humans increasingly rely on computational support to deal with data as a result of the increase in volume, complexity, and creation speed of data.

Still what is FAIR and what that means technically is still heavily debated/under construction (in the EU), nothing is set.

- community specific (implementation) strategies (FIPs, e.g. [CLARIN & ODISSEI](#))
- [OSTrails.eu](#)

Interoperable & vocabularies

- I2: (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow the FAIR principles

When we are describing data or metadata, we often use **vocabularies** that provide the terms or concepts that are adequate to represent their content.

However, if we use vocabularies in our data or metadata, *we should make sure that they are also FAIR in their own right so that others, humans or machines, can find, access, interoperate and reuse them.* The controlled vocabulary used to describe datasets needs to be documented and resolvable using globally unique and persistent identifiers. This documentation needs to be easily findable and accessible by anyone who uses the dataset.

FAIR assessment

- FAIR Implementation Profile

I1	Which knowledge representation languages (allowing machine interoperation) do you use for metadata records?	Knowledge representation language
I1	Which knowledge representation languages (allowing machine interoperation) do you use for datasets?	Knowledge representation language
I2	Which structured vocabularies do you use to annotate your metadata records?	Structured vocabularies
I2	Which structured vocabularies do you use to encode your datasets?	Structured vocabularies
I3	Which models, schema(s) do you use for your metadata records?	Metadata schema
I3	Which models, schema(s) do you use for your datasets?	Data schema

- vocabularies, schemas, ontologies (= semantic artifacts)
- are these only limited to the Linked Data domain?
 - we (will) have lot of (legacy) data that is valuable and should be available in a FAIR manner
 - also these have semantic artefacts, e.g. XSD
 - FAIR tends to have a RDF/LD focus, but needs to go beyond that

FAIR Assessment: Interoperability & vocabularies

- Interoperability assessment currently happens only very limited
 - focuses on metadata
 - [FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment Metrics](#)
 - FAIR & FATs: **the current (EU) frontier**
 - [OSTrails: FAIR IF](#) mix & match tests from different FATs (FAIR Assessment Tools)
 - how to tell the which vocabs your (meta)data uses?
 - RDF [summarizer](#) (task)
 - beyond? bridge to the RDF domain layer?
- Semantic Artefact registries
 - [FAIRsharing.eu](#)
 - **SSH vocabulary Registry**
 - caching
 - common APIs
 - ...
- getting ready for the (semantic) interoperability (assessment) of data

- FAIR assessment of your vocabulary
 - [FOOPs](#)

Vocabulary reuse

The importance of vocabulary reuse

- One of the best practices in vocabulary development is to re-use existing vocabularies (not only value vocabularies, but also data models)
- Re-use is determined by context and purpose
- Re-use can range from
 - very simple steps
 - adding URIs for concepts
 - re-using entire schemas/data models, and or specific properties
 - to very complex ontology alignment cases (see Carriero et al., 2020)
 - beware: entailments might clash semantically (discussion)
- Recommended reading: Lisena et al., 2022

Example of schema reuse

Example of ontology re-use

Example of an ontology produced in a research context

<https://data.odeuropa.eu/ontology/>

The SSH Vocabulary Registry

Summary until now

FAIR vocabulary registry & recommender

Today we are launching the production version!

<https://registry.vocabs.clariah.nl/>

- Idea started during CLARIAH-Core (2022)
- The purpose was to compile existing vocabularies in the SSH domain
 - Only the Awesome lists (Humanities and SSH existed) & Yalc selection
- Main developers:
 - Menzo Windhouwer
 - Kerim Meijer
- Development continues in [SSHOC.nl](https://sshoc.nl)

SSH FAIR Vocabulary Registry [About](#) [Guidelines](#) [FAQ](#) [HowTos](#) [Release notes](#) [Publications](#)

TEXT SEARCH

40 results, page 1 of 4 pages [Register new vocabulary](#)

Selected facets: [Reset facets](#)

None

AGROVOC Core [Owl](#)

Since the early 1980's, the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) has coordinated AGROVOC, a valuable tool for classifying data homogeneously, facilitating interoperability and reuse. AGROVOC is a multilingual and controlled vocabulary designed to cover concepts and terminology under FAO's areas of interest. It is the largest Linked Open Data set about agriculture available for public use and its greatest impact is through providing the access and visibility of data across... [Show more](#)

An ontology about letter corresponding [Rdfs](#)

Formal description of letter corresponding, related classes, and properties.

Basic Formal Ontology (BFO) [Owl](#)

The Basic Formal Ontology (BFO) is a small, upper level ontology that is designed for use in supporting information retrieval, analysis and integration in scientific and other domains. BFO is a genuine upper ontology. Thus it does not contain physical, chemical, biological or other terms which would properly fall within the coverage domains of the special sciences. BFO is used by more than 250 ontology-driven endeavors throughout the world. The BFO project was initiated in 2002 under the auspice... [Show more](#)

ENTITY

- ontology (32)
- list (3)
- thesaurus (2)
- authority file (1)
- gazetteer (1)

ENTITY

- Concept (26)
- Person (6)
- Place (2)
- Time-Span (2)
- Event-Activity (1)
- Organisation (1)

TOPIC (NWO)

- Librarianship, archive studies (4)

Basic approach

- the registry is metadata only, i.e., all vocabs "live" somewhere else ... has an owner/home outside of the registry ... unless it "died" than we have still a cache
- we add common APIs as far as possible, e.g., SKOSMOS for SKOS, SPARQL for any RDF-based vocab
- the registry is for more than just vocabularies, but for any semantic artifacts, i.e. including schema's models, ontologies, etc. (this is a main difference with Termennetwerk)
- as not all datasets will become LD, we also want to cater for semantic artifacts for other data representations like XML or CSV
- as there are unlimited ways a homepage for a vocab might look and lead to a download of the actual vocab, there is still a lot manual/semi-automatic labour going on, and, as many other similar registries do, we have to revisit the vocab from time to time to curate our entry ... we're working to make this move to automatic more and more ...

Vocabularies in the SSH FAIR Vocabulary Registry

- Initially, in 2023, it included most vocabularies from two curated lists:
 - [Awesome Ontologies for Digital Humanities](#) (ca. 40 vocabs)
 - [YALC: a registry of Linked Open Datasets](#) (ca. 126 vocabs)
- Vocabulary metadata is stored in XML (using a CMDI profile)
 - <https://www.clarin.eu/content/cmdr-component-metadata-infrastructure>
- Not all vocabularies are FAIR
- We have been working on:
 - Selecting most relevant ones
 - Adding more metadata
 - and creating/adapting the vocabulary metadata using existing vocabularies (e.g., VOID, DCAT, MOD)
 - Testing download / Improving workers

FAIR vocabulary registry & recommender (architecture overview)

Repositories:

- <https://github.com/CLARIAH/vocab-workers>
- <https://github.com/CLARIAH/vocab-registry>
- <https://github.com/CLARIAH/vocab-registry-editor>
- <https://github.com/CLARIAH/vocab-registry-docs>
- (vocabulary recommender temporarily in development in private Gitlab)

Recent paper:

Meijer, K. and Windhouwer, M. (2024). The CLARIAH FAIR Vocabulary Registry. CLARIN Annual Conference Proceedings, page 154. https://www.clarin.eu/sites/default/files/CLARIN2024_ConferenceProceedings_final.pdf

Roadmap

Current work in progress:

- Inventorizing & adding existing vocabularies in SS and Humanities
- Making the vocabulary metadata schema also FAIR
- Defining workflows (accepting/rejecting suggested vocabs, curation)
- User evaluation
- Documentation pages / Guidelines

Future development ([public roadmap in progress](#)):

- Browser/website technical and usability improvements
- Continue developing the **vocabulary recommender**
- Implement APIs (OpenRefine, Lenticular Lens)
- Work on specificities for non-RDF vocabularies
- Integrate to INEO portal
- Integrate FAIR assessment scores for vocabularies

FAIR vocabulary recommender (in the roadmap)

<https://recommender.vocabs.dev.clariah.nl/>

- scoring of a vocab to be based on:
 - Automatically checks on whether a vocabulary exists in other registries (e.g., Bartoc or LOV)
 - Registry gets user reviews (stars and comments)
 - Recommender Processes these inputs and give recommendations
 - Also recommendations based on user-provided csv (schema)

The screenshot shows the 'Add a review' modal in the Clariah FAIR Vocabulary Registry. The modal title is 'Add a review' and it is for the 'General Ontology for Linguistic Description (GOLD)'. It features a five-star rating system with all five stars selected. A text input field contains the comment 'Awesome!'. At the bottom right of the modal is a 'Post review' button. The background shows the 'General Ontology (GOLD)' page with a 'Register new vocabulary' button in the top right corner.

The screenshot shows the 'Vocabulary Recommender' interface. It has a search bar with a dropdown menu showing 'all', 'lov', and 'birth', and a search button. Below the search bar, it indicates '94 results'. A table displays the results with columns for IRI, Vocabulary, Description, Score, and Category.

IRI	Vocabulary	Description	Score	Category
bio:Birth	bio	The event of a person entering into life.	1.00	class
bio:birth	bio	El evento del nacimiento de una persona, grupo u organización	1.00	property

common "mis" understandings

- are you similar to termennetwerk?
 - the termennetwerk is a federated search engine on top of cultural heritage (SKOS) vocabs
 - the registry is broader, but once enough facets and APIs are in place one could "mimic" a similar approach, i.e. filter on all SKOS vocabs AND all vocabs relevant for the cultural heritage domain and get their SKOSMOS endpoints or Named graphs
 - the termennetwerk and NDE put a lot of effort in getting relevant vocabs into SKOS and to get collection management software companies to add support for the termennetwerk-based functionality into their products ... we take what is already there , but might also register the (SKOS) vocabs that are in the termennetwerk at some point
- ...

Publish vocabularies: vocabulary registry

- Once your vocab is stable and in use by (FAIR) (meta)data(sets)
 - <https://registry.vocabs.clariah.nl/>
- What are/will be the criteria to include a vocab?
 - completeness
 - (usage) description
 - license is explicit
 - governance is clear
 - persistency/versioning policy is clear
 - ...

Hands-on with the SSH vocabulary registry

Open this questionnaire

edu.nl/ykctd

extra

Figure 3b
Versioning Propagated
UPWARDS

Figure 4b
Versioning Propagated
DOWNWARDS

SKG-IF Overview

<https://zenodo.org/records/15309838>

<https://zenodo.org/records/14794901>

reuse

- RDFS and beyond add reasoning capabilities
 - range <- prop -> domain
 - using the prop has impact on the subject and/or object
 - ...
- reusing an ontology also takes over inference
- mixing & matching multiple ontologies might lead to incompatible inferences
- still try to reuse as much as possible ;-)

<http://workingontologist.org/>

Firefox File Edit View History Bookmarks Tools Window Help Tue 3 Jun 11:31

http://localhost:7200/repository/create/graphdb

Create GraphDB repository

GraphDB

- Import
- Explore
- SPARQL
- Monitor
- Setup**
 - Repositories
 - Users and Access
 - ACL Management
 - My Settings
 - Connectors
 - Cluster
 - Plugins
 - Namespaces
 - Autocomplete
 - RDF Rank

Repository ID*

Repository description

Read-only

Inference and Validation

Ruleset

- No inference
- RDFS (Optimized)
- RDFS
- RDFS-Plus (Optimized)**
- OWL-Horst (Optimized)
- OWL-Horst
- OWL2-QL (Optimized)
- OWL2-QL
- OWL-Max (Optimized)
- OWL-Max
- OWL2-RL (Optimized)
- OWL2-RL

Entity ID size 32-bit 40-bit

Enable context index

Enable predicate list index

Enable full-text search (FTS) index

FTS indexes to build (comma delimited)

FTS index for xsd:string literals

Repository GLOBALISE

Location: Local

Type: Graphdb

Access: Read/write

Total statements: 49,355

Explicit: 49,181

Inferred: 174

Expansion ratio (total/explicit): 1.00